

MALAVIKAGNIMITRAM: A HALLMARK OF KALIDASA'S CRAFTMANSHIP.

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Abstracts:

Kalidasa shows a new path to the world literature in general and India in particular. He was a great scholar and he showed his genius through his works. His compositions shows his knowledge on the Vedas, the Puranas, the Ramayana, the Mahabharata, the Vyakarana, the Alankarashastra, Philosophy etc. In the drama Malavikagnimitram also the poet very beautifully delineated the female characters. An important aspect of Kalidasa's compositions in his perfection on sketching the characters of his writings. Kalidasa was an ardent worshiper of Lord Shiva, as it can be felt in his compositions. Malavikagnimitram is the first drama written by the famous poet Kalidasa. As a tribute to Kalidasa, it is frequently referred to as Kalidasa Malavikagnimitram . The exquisite mystery play enthralls its audience, and keeps them hooked to the page until the very end.

Key Words:

Audience, Characters, Composition, Delineated, Drama, Enthralls Literature, Malavikagnimitra, Perfection, Sketching.

Introduction:

Malavikagnimitram tells the story of the love of Agnimitra, the Shunga Emperor at Vidisha for the beautiful hand maiden of his chief queen. He falls in love with the picture of an exiled servant girl named Malavika. He must resort to the help of his jester and play a game of subterfuge merely to look at the new girl. When the queen discovers her husband's passion for this girl, she becomes infuriated and has Malavika imprisoned, but as fate would be it, in the end she is discovered to be of royal birth and is accepted as one of his queens. The play contains an account of the Rajasuya sacrifice performed by Pushyamitra Shunga and an elaborate exposition of a theory on Music and acting.¹

The love triangle between king Agnimitra and Malavika is the central topic of Malvikagnimitram. The play's base is historical, yet its concept is so exalted that it provides a great deal of artistic diligent. Agnimitra's sensual sentences are laden with passionate sensations, which are shared by the readers as they read the poem. The narrative is a comedy about a king and a lowly maid who have a romantic relationship. It tells the story of King Agnimitra's love for Malavika, a never before seen royal maid. This lady was believed to be talented in both dance and music. It's admirable how they manage issues that arise between them in the middle of be wilderment and jealousy. Malvikagnimitram is one of Kalidasa's best works with numerous sequences of light hearted comedy, bewilderment and confrontation.²

This Malvikagnimitram is Kalidasa's first & delightful effort. He is certainly genius when it comes to combining humor, uncertainty and romance in a pot pouter of romantic dramas. The play's continuity is enhanced by the seamless flow of events. Though the play, has several flaws. It nonetheless shows the hall mark of Kalidasa craftsmanship's on the Whole. Agnimitra, despite his enthusiasm, is a bit passive and enlists the assistance of his minister to win over Malavika and crown her as his queen. Dramatic work Malvikagnimitram mentions the Rajasuya Yajna of King Pusyamitra Shunga. Agnimitra was Pusyamitra's deserving son or prince Vasumitra. Agnimitra's heroic son is also mentioned in this drama.³

Different Characters of Malvikagnimitram: Agnimitram was Dakshina Nayaka who had many wives but still had feelings for Malavika the lovely dance. Nonetheless, he never betrays his primary wife Dharni or his ever suspicious wife Iravati. He was a courageous king who know how to conquer his adversaries. Malavika is the princess who accepts he r fate as a servant with grace. She adores the monarch but never goes over the line. Her beauty fortitude and dignity radiate through the entire action. Gautama, the king's comparison is too devoted to assisting him in winning his sweet heart Malavika. His upbeat personality attracts to and entertains. Dharni, the principal queen of Agnimitra, was arrogant and authorian, yet she had a kind heart. Agnimitra praises her for constantly attempting to make him happy.⁴

She sends her kid with Agnimitra's fathers Aswamedha horse without complaint. Kaushiki, Malavika's care taker, assists he in finding love but maintains great power by

being submissive until the proper moment comes to disclose Malavika's truth. She sends her kid with Agnimitra's father's Ashwamedha horse without complaint. Kaushiki Malavika's caretaker, assists her in finding love but maintains great power by being submissive until the proper moment comes to disclose Malavika's truth.⁵

After an invocation of the deity as an auspicious act, the stage manager and his assistant, in their conversation state that the play. In the first act two scholars, Ganadas and Hardatt, from the kingdom are shown fighting amongst each other to settle the question of who is more knowledgeable in the field of dance and drama. To solve this conflict king Agnimitra summons the chamber maid Malavika. It is made obvious that the king has some desires for her but he did not want to make them public as yet as he is already married to queen Dharini. Malavika was a student of Guru Ganadas, one of the best if you will.⁶

He thought of using her in case of any competition. This little secret was known to Agnimitra's childhood friend and the court entertainer Gautam. Gautam also know about king's little love crush on Malavika. It was in fact Gautam who sets up a competition between the two gurus so that he gets to see the much talked about Malavika finally. Side by side, a battle is planned against the king of Vidharbha, King's soldiers had captured his cousin Madhavan by the Madhavsens sister escaped the capture, Kanchuki takes care of the preparations of the dance competition while minister Amatya Vahtak prepares for the military attack. The king insists that Madhavsens sister, Parivrajika Kaushiti, should be present during the dance competition and her decision will be the final decision.⁷

In the exhibition, Malavika is allowed first to show her dance. The king has an opportunity to feast his eyes with the sight of Malavika as she sings and dances. As the sole purpose of arranging the exhibition has been achieved, further examination of the instructors' claims is postponed for the time being. Gautama's plan turns out to be successful and GuruGanadas chooses Malavika to represent him in the dance competition. She performs a graceful and charming chhalik paly act on a quartel written by Sharmistha. She looks so beautiful while dancing that the king cannot take his eyes off her. Even her voice enamors him, She sings about a beloved craving for her over. The king starts feeling like she is calling out to him and he loses himself into her song and

dance. When she finishes, Gautam sees on king's face that he was dying to see Malavika smiling. Gautam makes a joke in the court and everyone starts to laugh and Malavika also smiles a little before leaving. This makes the king very happy. He loses all interest in the competition now. He does not really want to see the other dancers. Just when the king thought that he could not take any of this dance competition and cannot hear to see anyone else sing or dance. Vaitalik arrives. He announces the commencement of the lunch.⁸

Two maid servants converse that Ganadasa won in the contest and the king is quite love-sick and Malavika is now the more carefully guarded by the Queen. Queen Kaushik's maid Samahitika and Madhukanika discusses the dance performance of Malavika and comes to a mutual consensus that she is going to win the competition hands down. They are also aware of King's feelings for her, so is everyone else in the kingdom. Now Malavika and Bakulavalika is sent to stand underneath the Asika tree by the chief queen Dharini to perform dohada. Doha was a ceremony of dancing which has the capacity of making the buds flower soon.⁹ The queen does not take part in the ceremony herself as her feet were hurting after a fall from the swing but she promises Malavika that if the tree blossoms then she will grant Malavika a wish of hers. At this time queen Iravati invites the king to come into the pleasure garden and spend some time with her. But the king was worried that he might not be able to be himself in front of his queens now that he had this burning desire for Malavika. But Gautam suggested him to not leave the side of his queens and continue being the same with them. There comes a point where the king, Gautam, Iravati, Bakulvalika and Malavika all come face to face in the pleasure garden.¹⁰

In Act IV, the king had sent the Vidushaka to obtain news of Malavika. Iravati called upon queen Dharini and informed her of what had happened. There upon Dharini as her suggestion had Malavika and Vakulvahika put into a cellar as prisoners, and orders were issued to their guard that they were not to be released. Unless the queen's own snake seal ring was produced by the messenger as guarantee of good faith. The Vidushaka devises an ingenious scheme to procure their release, the other scene, queen Dharini is nursing her injured leg and is attended upon by the oarivajika, Vidushaka pretends he is bitten by a serpent when he was plucking flowers for the queen. For the

treatment, physician Dhruvasiddhi asks for a snake object for an healing procedure. The unsuspecting queen hands the snake ring. Then king is called upon on a false message of urgent business by the minister and leaves.¹¹

By showing the signal ring the guard, Malavika and Vakul Valika were set at liberty. King goes to meet Malavika and Vidushaka mounts guard outside but falls asleep which is observed by the passing guard and reports it to queen Iravati. Iravati goes there in hope of finding the king but finds Malavika, Bakulavika and the king and knows about the whole scheme. While the king is in a fix as to what to do or say next, they hear the news of princess Vasulakshmi's accident. They deport Malavika hopes that the Asoka would blossom within five days and have the kindness of the queen which it did.¹²

In Act v, we see that in the presence of the king, the queen, Malavika, and others two captive maid-servants brought from the Vidarbha expedition are introduced, who at once recognize Malavika as the missing sister of Madhavasena. The minister of Madhavasena, Sumati in the confusion of Madhavasena's capture, took flight with Malavika and his own sister. But Sumati was attacked by highwaymen while on his way to Agnimitra's capital, and Malavika and Sumati's sister were separated. Sumati's sister turned into parivrajala and attained herself to Dharini's court.¹³

Meanwhile, Malavika was secured by Virasena and sent to Dhaini as a gift, Parivrajika recognizes Malavika, but did not give out the identity of Malavika as Malavika was prophesied to remain for a year as a servant and then be married to a suitable husband. It is now proposed to bestow one half of the kingdom of Yajnasena on Madhavasena. News is also brought of the victory of Agnimitra's son. Vasumitra who was employed by Agnimitra's father Puspamita to guard his sacrificial horse. The queen in knowing all these and her promise to reward Malavika gives her to the king and gladly consents to their union. After this happy termination of the courtship of the royal love, the play ends with the customary Bharatvakya which here takes the form of an expression of general peace and happiness among the king's subjects.¹⁴

Thus, Malavikagnimitram is the first play of Kalidasa composed in five Acts. It is the story of King Agnimitra's love for Malavika, an unknown beautiful girl living in the royal harem. She was proficient in music & dance. This play is a court comedy of royal

love, in which harem, jealousies and court intrigues mingle to raise romantic situations of love, amusing scenes of confrontation and a merry, light-hearted air which are thoroughly enjoyable. It is truly the author's ingenuity, skill and ability for scheming that enable Agnimitra to meet Malavika and finally win her as his wife and queen. In spite of his political direction in matters of state, Agnimitra appears as a passive hero, thoroughly dependent on Vidushaka his minister for the success of his love affair. Kalidasa's skill in creating dramatic situations, as beyond doubt.¹⁵ Despite several defects, the play bears the unmistakable stamp in Kalidasa's workmanship. Thus the Malavikagnimitra is essentially a love play, it is not only the shortest, but also the earliest of Kalidasa's dramas, probably the earliest of all his works.

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